

Improving Attitude And Achievements Of Biology Students In Senior Secondary Schools Through Heuristic Inquiry Method

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ABSTRACT

This study was motivated by the need to enhance students' attitudes and achievements in biology by investigating the effectiveness of the heuristic inquiry method as an interactive and student-centered approach to learning. Therefore, the study investigated the effects of Heuristic Inquiry Method on Attitude and Achievement of Senior Secondary Biology Students in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, Nigeria. The research design used was quasi-experimental using pre-test and post-test control group approach. Two research questions and two null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance. The population of the study consisted of 26,338 (10,338 Male and 16,000 Female) SS II Biology students in the six Area Councils of Federal Capital Territory, Abuja. The sample size consisted of 84 SS II Biology students (43 for the experimental group and 41 for the control group) from two selected senior secondary schools in Abuja Municipal Area Council Educational Zone. The instruments for data collection were Biology Achievement Test (BAT) and Biology Attitude Questionnaire (BAQ) validated by experts. The reliability of the Biology Attitude Questionnaire was determined using Cronbach Alpha which gave an index of 0.72, while the Biology Achievement test was determined using Kuder Richardson KR-20 and reliability co-efficient obtain was 0.87. Descriptive statistics were used to answer the two research questions, while Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was used to test the null hypotheses. The findings revealed that there was a significant difference in the attitudes of Biology students exposed to the heuristic inquiry method and their counterparts taught with the conventional method; there was a significant difference in students' academic achievement taught Biology with heuristic inquiry method and their counterpart taught conventional method. Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that the heuristic inquiry method has a positive effect on students' attitudes, and academic achievement. Hence, it was recommended that regular workshops, seminars, and conferences should be held for teachers to make them familiar with the knowledge of the heuristic inquiry method and thus should be encouraged to use it in their classroom for lesson delivery.

Keywords: Biology, attitude, achievement, heuristic inquiry method.

INTRODUCTION

Biology plays a vital role in the economic development of a nation. Biology is one of the science subjects that secondary school students offer at the senior levels in Nigerian secondary schools in order to acquire relevant knowledge, adequate laboratory skills so that they become useful members of the society. Biology is a branch of science which deals with the study of living things. It is also a prerequisite for

higher learning in a number of science related professional courses like medicine, zoology, botany, biochemistry and microbiology. Apart from career opportunities from biological studies, the subject has also contributed in areas relating to livestock raising through cross breeding of various varieties of plant and animal species, development of vaccines and drugs for preventing and curing diseases, increase in food production and awareness of genetic diseases. Indeed, it is worthy that biology has contributed to national development through its various uses to mankind.

Despite the importance of biology to national development, researchers such Nwagbo, Chikelu and Okoro (2019), Dajal and Mohammed (2019) reported that the low achievement rate of students in biology in National Examinations such the West African Senior Secondary School Certificate Examination (WASSCE) is a reflection of the disconnection between teacher and their students, hence the need for a new approach to bridge the gap in classroom learning. The West African Examination Council (WAEC) Chief Examiner's report (2020) noted that the persistent poor achievement of students in biology at Senior School Certificate Examination (S.S.C.E) leaves one in doubt about the effectiveness of instructional methods used by the biology teachers for the teaching and learning of biology. The low achievement of biology students is an indication that it is either biology teachers do not utilize student-centered approaches to teach, or there are other factors which possibly affect achievement. Some of these factors put forward by researchers as potentially impacting achievement include; method of teaching, attitudinal problems of students, cognitive and socio-economic problems of teachers.

Heuristics inquiry method is a process of learning that is driven by questioning, thoughtful investigating, and making sense of information and developing new understanding (Sanchita, 2023). It facilitates acquiring skills and attitudes for biology students to seek resolutions to questions and issues while constructing new knowledge. This method is more focused on using and learning content as a means to develop information processing and problem solving skills. Heuristic inquiry method is more students centered. Students are more engaged in construction of knowledge through active involvement. Students are involved in an open system classroom where they are encouraged to search and make use of resources beyond the classroom and the school.

According to Nwafor, Okpala and Oka (2019), heuristic inquiry method is a teaching method that combines the curiosity of students and the scientific method to enhance the development of critical thinking and process skills while learning science. Teaching of science through heuristic inquiry method is the cornerstone of good teaching to improve students' attitude and achievement to biology. Through effective heuristic inquiry approach, students are expected to improve in science process skills acquisition and also exhibit more positive attitudes towards science. The students are expected to take responsibility for their learning and begin to think like scientists.

Based on this background therefore, this study was designed to investigate the effects of heuristic inquiry method on attitude and achievement of senior secondary Biology students in Federal Capital Territory (FCT), Abuja, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Students in senior secondary schools demonstrate undesirable attitudes toward Biology even though this subject establishes foundations for medical, scientific, agricultural and technological careers yet they do not meet their expected achievements on internal and external tests. The traditional educational practices which do not engage students nor support critical thinking appear responsible for students who show both weak academic performance and limited interest in Biology education.

Conventional teacher-centered approaches dominate classroom instruction, leaving little room for inquiry, or problem-solving, which are essential for meaningful learning in science. As a result, students become passive recipients of knowledge, lacking motivation and interest in learning Biology. This situation not only hinders academic success but also discourages students from pursuing science-related disciplines.

In response to these challenges, there is a need to find new instructional approaches that can promote students' attitude as well as improve academic achievement in Biology. The heuristic inquiry method, which emphasizes discovery learning, problem-solving, and active participation, holds promise as an effective pedagogical approach. Therefore, this study investigated the effects of heuristic inquiry method in improving senior secondary Biology students' attitude and achievement scores in order to establish if

heuristic inquiry method can serve as a suitable teaching methodology substitute for regular conventional teaching method in enhancing students' attitude and achievement in Biology.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to investigate the effects of heuristic inquiry method on attitude and achievement of senior secondary Biology students. Specifically, the objectives of the study were to:

- i. find out the difference in the mean attitude scores of students taught Biology using heuristic inquiry method and their counterparts taught using conventional method; and
- ii. ascertain the difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught Biology using heuristic inquiry method and those taught using conventional methods;

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study:

1. What is the difference in the mean attitude scores of students taught Biology using heuristic inquiry method and their counterparts taught using conventional method?
2. What is the difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught Biology using heuristic inquiry method and those taught using conventional method?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significant.

HO1: There is no significant difference in the mean attitude scores of students taught Biology using heuristic inquiry method and their counterparts taught using conventional method.

HO2: There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught Biology using heuristic inquiry method and those taught using conventional method.

METHODOLOGY

The research design of this study was quasi-experimental that specifically, applied pre-test, post-test non-randomized control group. This design was chosen in order to ensure thorough manipulation of the variables in the study. The population of the study comprised twenty-six thousand, three hundred and thirty-eight (26,338) SS II Biology students in the six Area councils in FCT, Abuja (Computer statistics Unit, SEB, 2024).

A sample size of eighty four (84) Biology students were used for the study; multi-stage sampling procedure was adopted in selecting the sample size of the study.

Instrumentation

The instruments used for data collection were Biology Achievement Test (BAT) and Biology Attitude Questionnaire (BAQ) designed by the researcher. The Biology Achievement Test (BAT) was used for pre-test and post-test and it comprised of twenty-five (25) items multiple choice objective test questions with four (4) options lettered A, B, C and D. The test items were based on concepts of class of conservation of natural resources, pollution and flower.

The Biology Attitude Questionnaire (BAQ) was used for attitude testing before and after the treatment. The BAQ consisted of 25 items constructed on 4 point rating scale responses of Strongly Agree SA=4, Agree A=3, Disagree D=2, Strongly Disagree SD=1 for positive statements while the ratings were reversed for negative statements.

The Instruments, Biology Attitude Questionnaire (BAQ) and Biology Achievement Test (BAT) were subjected to both face and content validity. The validation of these instruments was done by three experts, one from Department of Science and Environmental Education who checked the construct validity, two qualified and experienced biology teachers from the sampled school selected checked the face validity.

After the validation the BAQ and BAT were subjected to pilot test to ascertain the reliability of the instruments. The researcher conducted a pilot test using one intact class of forty (40) students in a school that was not part of the sample selected. The reliability of the Biology Attitude Questionnaire was determined using Cronbach Alpha which gave an index of 0.72, while the Biology Achievement Test was also pilot tested in the same school. The scores obtained from the students were used to determine the internal consistency and reliability co-efficient of 0.87 was obtained using Kuder-Richardson (KR-20)

formula. The choice of Kuder-Richardson (KR-20) was because the instrument was dichotomously scored and was not of the same difficulty.

Data Collection Procedure

The data were collected with the help of two research assistants, biology teachers from the sampled schools. Prior to the commencement of the treatment BAT and BAQ were administered to the students in experimental and control groups as pre-test. The responses of the students were marked with the scores recorded to determine their entry attitude and achievement. Single lessons of 40 minutes per three days of the week were taught both to the experimental and control groups in biology for six (6) weeks. The experimental group were taught biology concepts using heuristic inquiry strategy by the trained research assistant, while the control group was taught by other trained research assistants using conventional method.

At the end of the six (6) weeks' treatment, the BAQ and BAT were administered immediately to the experimental and control groups. The scripts were marked and scored with the use of marking scheme and each question was awarded 2 marks and the total obtainable was 50 marks. The marks obtained from the pre-test and post-test via the instruments (BAT) was used as data for this study. The data collected from the study were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The Research questions were answered using, frequency counts, means and standard deviations while ANCOVA statistics at 0.05 level of significance was used to test the hypotheses.

RESULTS

Research Question One: *What is the difference in the mean attitude scores of students taught Biology using heuristic inquiry method and their counterparts taught using conventional method?*

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of Achievement scores of Biology students in experimental and control groups

Groups	N	Pre-test \bar{X}	SD	Post-test \bar{X}	SD	Mean Gain
Experimental	43	18.56	2.80	36.05	4.98	17.49
Control	41	19.46	3.00	30.93	4.51	11.47
Mean Difference Total	84	-0.90		5.12		6.02

Table 2 showed the mean and standard deviation on pre-test and post-test achievement scores in respect to groups. From the results obtained, students in experimental group had a mean achievement score of 18.56 with a standard deviation of 2.80 for pre-test while for the post-test was 36.05 and 4.98 respectively. However, the mean and standard deviation for the students in control group was 19.46 and 3.00 in the pre-test, while that for the post-test was 30.93 and 4.51 respectively. Again, the mean gain for experimental and control group are 17.49 and 12.04 respectively. The overall mean difference between the groups was 6.02. This shows that there was a difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught using heuristic inquiry method in experimental group and their counterparts taught using conventional method in control group.

Test of Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance

HO1: There is no significant difference in the mean attitude scores of Biology students taught using heuristic inquiry method and their counterparts taught using conventional method.

Table 3: ANCOVA Analysis of mean attitude scores between the Experimental and Control Groups

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	.956 ^a	2	.478	8.769	0.000
Intercept	1.775	1	1.775	32.557	0.000
Treatment	.878	1	.878	16.103	0.000
Pretest	.090	1	.090	1.655	0.202
Error	4.415	81	.055		
Total	618.865	84			
Corrected Total	5.371	83			

Table 3 shows the summary of ANCOVA analysis of mean attitude scores of Biology students taught using heuristic inquiry method and their counterparts taught using conventional method. The result from the table revealed that $F(1, 83) = 16.103$ and $P = 0.000$ for the main treatment. The significant p-value (0.00) was less than 0.05 level of significant ($p < 0.05$). Thus the hypothesis was rejected. Hence, there was significant difference in the mean attitude scores of Biology students taught using heuristic inquiry method and their counterparts taught using conventional method in favour of experimental group.

HO2: There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of Biology students taught heuristic inquiry method and those taught using conventional method.

Table 4: ANCOVA Analysis of Mean Achievement Scores of Students in Experimental and Control groups

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	603.083 ^a	2	301.542	13.511	.000
Intercept	1488.594	1	1488.594	66.700	.000
Pretest Group	52.961	1	52.961	2.373	.127
	590.603	1	590.603	26.464	.000
Error	1807.726	81	22.318		
Total	96948.000	84			
Corrected Total	2410.810	83			

Table 4 shows the summary of ANCOVA analysis of mean achievement scores of Biology students taught using heuristic inquiry method and their counterparts taught using conventional method. The result from the table revealed that $F(1, 83) = 26.464$ and $P = 0.000$ for the main treatment. The significant p-value (0.00) was less than 0.05 level of significant ($p < 0.05$). Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected. Hence, there was significant difference in the mean achievement scores of Biology students taught using heuristic inquiry method and those taught using conventional method.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings of the study revealed that the mean attitude scores of students taught Biology using heuristic inquiry method differ significantly leading to better achievement than those taught conventional method.

Also the test of hypotheses confirmed that there was significant difference in the mean attitude scores of Biology students taught using heuristic inquiry method than their counterparts taught conventional method. This finding confirms the findings of Nwafor, Okpala and Oka (2019) who in their study found that exposure of the learners to heuristic inquiry method have been found to positively affect the enhancement of students' attitude towards Biology. The findings also give support to those of Sanchita (2023), who found significant difference in favour of the experimental group. Similarly, research conducted by Shashi (2022) showed that heuristic inquiry method enhanced attitude in learning, mastery and meaningful learning that can increase performance. The reason for the significant difference between the mean attitude scores of two groups was because heuristic inquiry motivates students to interact effectively with one another giving them opportunity to engage better in the learning attitudes or activities.

The findings of the study revealed that the academic achievement of students taught Biology using heuristic inquiry method achieved significantly greater than their counterparts taught biology using conventional method. This findings was confirmed by the result of hypothesis which revealed that there was significant difference in the mean achievement scores of Biology students taught using heuristic inquiry method and their counterparts taught conventional method. The finding confirms those of Wakhata, Mutarutinya and Balimuttajjo (2022) who in their study reported that exposure of the learners to heuristic inquiry method have been found to positively affect the enhancement of students' achievement in Biology. The findings also lend support to those of Anekwe, Opara and Nnorom (2021), Oka and Abba (2020), who found significant difference in favour of the experimental group. Similarly, research conducted by Cacay (2022) showed that heuristic inquiry method enhances attitude in learning, mastery and meaningful learning that can increase achievement. The reason for the significant difference between the mean achievements scores of two groups could be as a result that heuristic inquiry method is activity oriented teaching method that encourage active participation of students in the class room activities and as well maximize comprehension of subject matter.

On the other hand, the findings contradict the findings of Mehmet (2020) which revealed that male students' achievement were significantly higher than that of their female counterpart exposed to three (3) interaction patterns (cooperative, competitive and individualistic patterns of learning); this difference may be due to the low achievement and lack of active participation of some female students.

CONCLUSION

It was concluded that the use of heuristic inquiry method enhanced the academic achievement of students in Biology as well as boost their attitude than the conventional method.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study the following recommendations were made:

1. Biology teachers should be encouraged to incorporate heuristic inquiry method of teaching since the method provides the opportunity of engaging students in learning activities and this affects their achievement and attitude towards Biology concepts.
2. Stakeholders and relevant professional bodies like Science Teachers Association of Nigeria (STAN) should organize seminars, workshops and conferences for Biology teachers to adopt the use of heuristic inquiry teaching methods in the teaching of biology.

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